

T-Test

Notes

Output Created		01-MAR-2024 12:33:18
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\Jonathan\Documents\Course Work\AntsAnalysis\SimData.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	6023
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each analysis are based on the cases with no missing or out-of-range data for any variable in the analysis.
Syntax		T-TEST GROUPS=Type(1 2) /MISSING=ANALYSIS /VARIABLES=SmlArenaPerm MedArenaPerm LrgArenaPerm /ES DISPLAY(TRUE) /CRITERIA=CI(.95).
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.53

[DataSet1] C:\Users\Jonathan\Documents\Course Work\AntsAnalysis\SimData.sav

Group Statistics

	Type	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
SmlArenaPerm	Beacon	3003	308.9703	53.26639	.97202
	Random	3003	306.7501	53.26639	.97202
MedArenaPerm	Beacon	3003	485.6369	59.51838	1.08611
	Random	3003	440.8990	59.51838	1.08611
LrgArenaPerm	Beacon	3003	585.4842	41.46967	.75675
	Random	3003	512.8244	41.46967	.75675

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means	
		F	Sig.	t	df
SmlArenaPerm	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	1.615	6004
	Equal variances not assumed			1.615	6004.000
MedArenaPerm	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	29.126	6004
	Equal variances not assumed			29.126	6004.000
LrgArenaPerm	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	67.893	6004
	Equal variances not assumed			67.893	6004.000

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		Significance		Mean Difference
		One-Sided p	Two-Sided p	
SmlArenaPerm	Equal variances assumed	.053	.106	2.22018
	Equal variances not assumed	.053	.106	2.22018
MedArenaPerm	Equal variances assumed	<.001	<.001	44.73795
	Equal variances not assumed	<.001	<.001	44.73795
LrgArenaPerm	Equal variances assumed	<.001	<.001	72.65978
	Equal variances not assumed	<.001	<.001	72.65978

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
			Lower	Upper
SmlArenaPerm	Equal variances assumed	1.37465	-.47462	4.91497
	Equal variances not assumed	1.37465	-.47462	4.91497
MedArenaPerm	Equal variances assumed	1.53599	41.72685	47.74904
	Equal variances not assumed	1.53599	41.72685	47.74904
LrgArenaPerm	Equal variances assumed	1.07021	70.56179	74.75777
	Equal variances not assumed	1.07021	70.56179	74.75777

Independent Samples Effect Sizes

		Standardizer ^a	Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower	Upper
SmlArenaPerm	Cohen's d	53.26639	.042	-.009	.092
	Hedges' correction	53.27304	.042	-.009	.092
	Glass's delta	53.26639	.042	-.009	.092
MedArenaPerm	Cohen's d	59.51838	.752	.699	.804
	Hedges' correction	59.52582	.752	.699	.804
	Glass's delta	59.51838	.752	.698	.806
LrgArenaPerm	Cohen's d	41.46967	1.752	1.693	1.812
	Hedges' correction	41.47485	1.752	1.692	1.811
	Glass's delta	41.46967	1.752	1.685	1.819

- a. The denominator used in estimating the effect sizes.
 Cohen's d uses the pooled standard deviation.
 Hedges' correction uses the pooled standard deviation, plus a correction factor.
 Glass's delta uses the sample standard deviation of the control (i.e., the second) group.